

Nurturing international scientific communities through accessible translated training material.

Target audience: Anyone who is in the process of hosting translated learning materials

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1. BioNT's automated and curated translation process

BioNT aims to enable broader accessibility of scientific training by supporting the translation of training materials into multiple languages (Spanish, German, Italian). The approach involves a hybrid system that combines AI-based translation (e.g., using DeepL or AI-assisted) with human curation and quality control. Translation efforts are organised per lesson, with coordinators responsible for each, ensuring accuracy, context preservation, and consistency in terminology. The key principles are:

- One-time curated translations tied to specific training dates (point-in-time when the training was provided).
- Parallel hosting of translations alongside the original materials when possible.
- Open and collaborative workflow using Git-based infrastructure.
- Integration of translated materials into the BioNT platform and external repositories (e.g., Galaxy Training Network (GTN) and The Carpentries).

2. Platforms Hosting the Learning Materials and Different Translation Alternatives

The training materials of the BioNT's basic curriculum are hosted either by The Carpentries or the Galaxy Training Network. Both networks have different material hosting strategies, and therefore, the BioNT translation hosting is different for both networks.

Galaxy Training Network (GTN)

- Supports versioning, translated user-interface (metadata) and language-specific materials.
- Translations are hosted in parallel with original content, within the same GitHub repository.
- Translation of metadata files is needed only to support new languages, for which BioNT contributed Italian and German.
- File naming uses language suffixes (e.g., tutorial_ES.md).
- Curated translations can be submitted back to GTN via pull requests.
- Navigation links to switch between different translated versions

The Carpentries

- Uses the Sandpaper workbench for building lessons.
- Translation via .po files (metadata) and lesson content via collaborative translation platforms such as Crowdin.
- Does not support versioning of content—only the latest version is live.
- Translations are maintained in separate repositories (one per lesson and language) under a BioNT GitHub organisation due to workbench limitations.
- Navigation menus to switch between different translated versions

3. Description of File Formats of the Learning Materials

BioNT training materials are primarily based on **Markdown (.md)** files. Depending on the platform, the file sources are different. The platforms host the lesson content as well as additional supporting files that depend on the platform infrastructure.

The GTN file formats:

File Type	Description	Content type
<code>tutorial.md</code>	Markdown file containing lesson content	Lesson material
<code>tutorial_[de,es,it].md</code>	Translated lesson materials marking the language and stored next to the original English tutorial.md file	Lesson material

<code>faq.md</code>	File containing snippets of repeating lesson content that will be included in many tutorials	Lesson/Platform material
<code>faq_[de,es,it].md</code>	Translation of the original faq.md file	Lesson/Platform material
<code>metadata/lang/[en,de,es,it].yaml</code>	Metadata YAML config files, which are needed for the training interface.	Platform material

The Carpentries file formats:

File Type	Description
<code>index.md</code>	Entry point and overview of the lesson
<code>episodes/*.md</code>	Main content chapters
<code>learners/*.md</code>	Setup and prerequisites for learners
<code>instructors/*.md</code>	Teaching notes and tips
<code>profiles/*.md</code>	Learner profiles and personas
<code>config.yaml</code>	Metadata, including language, title, and keywords

Note: While GTN includes all files and infrastructure in the same repository, The Carpentries' workbench is a purpose-built solution that bundles the supported languages. This meant that while for GTN, the inclusion of new languages could be done in a single location (see [metadata/lang/](#) above), for the workbench, languages had to be included in the software and released as part of official workbench versions before being able to generate fully translated materials for those target languages.

4. BioNT Automated Translation Pipeline

BioNT uses a semi-automated translation pipeline based on a [translate_md tool](#), which wraps around the **DeepL API**. The pipeline supports bulk translation of Markdown files while preserving formatting and code blocks. The tool tries to translate sections that are unarguably meant to be translated. Nested content, due to its resemblance to code blocks, may be kept untranslated. This is revised during the later curation process, which ensures

that missing or unnecessary translation is rectified. Acronyms or code-words are also verified. In particular, the latter were found to often be translated, in some languages more than others, despite being marked as not-for-translation. Included in this list are tool names and icons/emojis (in GTN materials) and callout headers or nested exercises (in workbench materials).

Core Features:

- Language-specific output folders
- Preservation of code snippets
- Optional glossary support via DeepL
- Semantic coherence by ingesting the full document as context.
- CLI-based batch processing (`translate_md` tool)

Translation pipeline (shell command):

```
# Translate top-level index.md to German
lang="de"

# Add the configuration language
echo "lang: $lang" >> config.yaml

# translate the index
translate_md --input-markdown-filestring 'index.md' --output-subdir --target-lang ${lang} --authentication-key
$DEEPL_AUTH_KEY

# Create an 'en' directory for top-level index.md if it doesn't exist
mkdir -p en
cp index.md en
cp ${lang}/index.md .

# Define an array of directories to process
directories=("episodes" "instructors" "profiles" "learners")

# Loop through each directory in the array
for dir in "${directories[@]}; do
    # Translate markdown files to Spanish
    translate_md --input-markdown-filestring "${dir}/*.md" --output-subdir --target-lang ${lang}
    --authentication-key $DEEPL_AUTH_KEY
    # Move into the directory
    cd "$dir"
    # Create an 'en' subdirectory if it doesn't exist, and copy original files into it
    mkdir -p en
    cp *.md en
    # Copy translated files (in 'es' subdirectory) to the current directory
    cp ${lang}/*.md .
    # Move back to the root directory
    cd ..
done
```

5. Curation of the Learning Materials

Each automated translation needs to be manually curated after completion:

Workflow for the GTN and Workbench lesson materials:

As both lesson frameworks are based on Markdown and the tools to generate the lesson are open-source, they can be previewed locally for validation and to ensure visual blocks are correctly rendered. Final versions are rendered with their respective GitHub-based infrastructures.

Common Markdown issues were encountered during curation. Some were more frequent with languages such as Italian and Spanish, and less with German. Possibly because German shares a closer root with- and incorporates English words.

Issues include:

- Icon and tool names and labels are translated - e.g., **{icon hammer}** becomes **{icono martello}** when it should be kept unchanged.
- Links are incorrectly translated - e.g., **[file-system](#file-system)** becomes **[sistema de archivos](#sistema-de-archivos)**, no longer matching the header that the link should point to.
- Context is incorrect, or no translation should take place - e.g. **[pipes](#unix-shell)** becomes **[tuberia](#unix-concha)**
- Missing matching braces, parentheses or parts of semantic constructs - e.g. **[tool name](#tool-name)** becomes **(#tool-name)**, omitting the **[tool-name]** part.
- Scrambled line breaks or white-space where it is semantically important - e.g. **{toc}** the Table of Contents, appearing in the same line as the content after translation instead of the line below it. This is visible by **{toc}** not rendering correctly in the final output and being shown literally instead of being replaced by the Table of Contents.
- Misaligned exercise blocks - e.g. the workbench uses a set of nested blocks where some are visible (instructions), and some are hidden (solutions). The automatic translation would occasionally make solutions visible by default.
- Pages or lessons with too little content suffer from incorrect translations due to a lack of context - e.g., instructor notes often mistranslate technical terms as those documents were briefer but still used jargon specific to the lesson.
- Incorrectly translated or non-translated blocks and headers - e.g., headers in GTN materials include learning objectives and outcomes, which are often missed and remain in English after translation. Similarly, code blocks with file or folder names should, in some cases, be translated, while in others they should not, as translating them breaks the flow or other content of the lesson.
- Images containing text - notoriously difficult, translating text in images requires re-creating the image and manually translating the content. A counterintuitive example was embedded SVG illustrations. SVGs are text, and while they could be translated, the automatic translation would occasionally translate tags or other elements, rendering the SVG incorrectly.

6. Translation hosting: Giving back to the platforms and communities

Platform	Hosting Approach	Contribution Back
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GTN	Within the GTN fork, PRs are submitted to upstream	Yes (via PR to GTN)
The Carpentries	Hosted under BioNT GitHub due to versioning constraints	The Carpentries doesn't yet host translated materials, hence there is currently no easy process to contribute upstream. Translations are linked to each other using a BioNT contributed drop-down feature.
BioNT Website	Deployed using GitLab Pages	Primary archive for project duration. The website acts as a content hub, including links to all lessons and their translations

7. Conclusion and Lessons Learned

Throughout the translation process, the workflow was not only established but also continuously adapted. The following section summarizes the key lessons learned:

- Markdown is a convenient format for editing and rendering of training material, but some of its content remains challenging to translate automatically due to ambiguous boundaries between what should and shouldn't be translated.
- Images are not easily translatable when text is embedded in the image. Text-based diagrams (e.g., [mermaid.js](#), PlantUML, Graphviz...) and even SVG are preferred formats for visual elements.
- Context is important. Automatic translation tools should allow side-loading of context or glossaries to ensure translation is semantically and contextually accurate.
- The curation process is work-intensive and requires frequent context switching between the original and the translation in order to identify differences and/or mistakes. Platform-assisted or man-in-the-middle translation platforms are expected to ease both the automatic translation and the curation of content. The approaches taken by The Carpentries with the Crowdin platform are one such example. Where sovereignty is desired, a platform such as Weblate (<https://weblate.org>) could be considered.
- Interconnecting and maintaining different translations is challenging, as corrections in one language may need to be considered for inclusion in other languages. While not a critical aspect for BioNT since English was the reference language, as communities grow around specific languages, considerations should be made and processes ideally implemented to allow such cross-feedback. With the recent advances in AI-assisted infrastructure, this aspect is likely to improve, and additional value will be brought into and out of current training material.